

HOW RELEVANT ARE LOAD RATE EFFECTS TO REALISTIC BONDED JOINTS?

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SUMMARY: Adhesive bonded repairs have been a feature of RAAF maintenance practice since the first bonded composite patch was applied to C-130-A in May 1975. The Royal Australian Air Force has recently issued RAAF Engineering Standard C5033, on Bonded and Composite Repairs, with the design procedures for bonded repairs based largely on modeling the repair as a bonded joint. Efforts to obtain international acceptance of the fundamental elements of the Standard have been highly successful.

Analytical techniques have advanced significantly since the first practical repair, leading to a plethora of studies into a range of phenomenological issues of relevance to the performance of bonded repairs. Some of these studies have advocated that load rate effects result in significant changes to the stress-strain behaviour of adhesive systems, and have even suggested that these effects are of fundamental importance to repair design methodology. This paper will show that although the phenomena reported does indeed occur under specific conditions, its relevance to practical repair designs is limited.

KEYWORDS: adhesive bonding, bonded joint design, load rate, strain hold, strength of bonded joints, bonded repair

INTRODUCTION

Adhesive bonded joints are playing an increasing role in construction of aircraft structures. Bonded repairs are also being used in an increasing number of applications for repair of metallic structure on both defence [1 to 5] and civil aircraft [1, 6]. Australia has pioneered the use of adhesive bonded repair for metallic structures with applications of bonded repairs to cracks, reinforcements and repairs to corrosion and lightning damage on a wide range of aircraft. Of interest, the Royal Australian Air Force (RAAF) will be the only operator to fly C-130E aircraft to life of type without changing wing skins, due to the judicious use of bonded patches to repair wide-spread stress corrosion cracking. This repair alone has been estimated to have saved \$66 million (1990 value).

The RAAF is now planning the adoption of bonded repairs as a standard repair process, to be used as an alternative to conventional mechanically fastened repairs. To ensure that the technology is correctly managed, RAAF has developed RAAF Engineering Standard C5033 which provides overall control of the use of bonded repair technology. Two handbooks addressing repair design and application technology are currently in final draft form, and training courses in repair familiarisation and repair design have been established to ensure that only appropriate adhesive bonding technology is applied to RAAF assets.

The RAAF ENG STD, the design handbook and the repair design course rely on simple analytical techniques to develop repairs with a high level of structural integrity. A simple calculation is used to differentiate between those repairs which can be repaired using simple methods and those requiring a higher level analysis. The approach used relies on analytical equations applicable to bonded joints [7]. Recent published work [8] questions the validity of the analytical methods on which RAAF ENG STD C5033 is based. This paper will show that the conclusions of the previous work are not valid, and that, even if they were valid, the approach used in ENG STD C5033 has sufficient conservatism to ensure that structural integrity for repairs is maintained.

SHEAR STRESSES IN A BONDED JOINT

Adhesive shear stresses in bonded joints result from the relative displacement of the members being joined (adherends). As a joint is loaded, the adherends move apart, causing shear strains. If the adherends are very stiff and inextensible, the shear strains (and hence the shear stresses) are uniform along the length of the joint, (see Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Shear in a bonded joint between inextensible adherends.

If such a joint is subject to increasing load, the adhesive will eventually pass its elastic limit, and plastic behaviour will occur. A typical shear stress-shear strain curve is shown in Fig. 2. This form of behaviour occurs in a Thick Adherend Test, used to characterise adhesive properties for joint design, (see ASTM D 3983-93). While this test is widely used for establishment of design values for adhesives, the stress-strain behaviour of all adhesives depends strongly on a range of factors, such as the test temperature [9]. At low temperatures, adhesives have a high shear modulus and a high shear strength, but are relatively brittle with minimal plastic behaviour. As the test temperature is increased, the shear strength and shear modulus decrease, and the plastic strain capacity increases.

Figure 2. Typical shear stress-shear strain curve for an adhesive, showing typical effects due to test temperature.

A similar change in adhesive properties for different test loading rates has been reported [10], and the test data supplied shows that load rates *do* change the stress strain behaviour of the adhesive in the particular test specimens used in the work. This paper intends to show that it is possible to design real bonded joints such that load rate effects are irrelevant.

SHEAR STRESSES IN REAL JOINTS

For realistic joints between adherends which are extensible, the displacements due to shear are increased by the displacements due to the strains generated in the adherends themselves [7] (see Fig. 3). The resulting shear stresses and strains are non-uniform, with high stresses occurring at each end of the joint. If the overlap length is large enough, the shear stresses will decay from the maximum at the ends to zero in the middle of the joint. As the joint load is increased, the adhesive at the ends of the joint is plastically deformed, and plastic zones will form at the ends of the joint. Again, provided the overlap length is large enough, the elastic trough will still exist. If the adhesive shear strain at the end of the joint exceeds the maximum shear strain capacity of the adhesive, then the adhesive will fail.

JOINT LOAD CAPACITY

Hart-Smith gives the *potential load capacity* of an adhesive in a bonded joint as:

$$P = \sqrt{4\eta\tau_p\left(\frac{1}{2}\gamma_e + \gamma_p\right)Et} \text{ ignoring bending and thermal stress effects.} \quad (1)$$

The variable η is the adhesive thickness, γ_e is the elastic strain limit, γ_p is the plastic strain capacity of the adhesive, τ_p is the plastic stress limit for the adhesive, E is the elastic modulus of the adherends and t is the thickness of the adherend. The adhesive variables are determined by the thick adherend test as discussed before. Note that this calculation addresses the potential load capacity, because for thin adherends, it is the adherend which may limit the strength of the joint, and not the adhesive. If the adhesive has a load capacity greater than the parent material, then it will not fail.

The term $\tau_p\left(\frac{1}{2}\gamma_e + \gamma_p\right)$ is the strain energy associated with joint failure.

Figure 3. Shear stresses in bonded joints between thin adherends.

As described in reference [8] the adhesive properties *will* change with different load rates. However, even though it noted the influence of the strain energy term in the load capacity of an adhesive bond, the work at reference [8] did not test the specimens to failure, because to do so would have damaged the extensometer used to measure shear strain. Thus the plastic shear

strain at failure γ_p was not measured, and no conclusion could be drawn in respect of the total strain energy.

Because the changes in shear stress-shear strain behaviour are similar to the changes caused by different test temperatures, it is very probable that changes would also occur in plastic shear strain at failure. One could easily expect that a response similar to that of a change in temperature could occur for load rate effects, where changes in plastic shear limit stresses and strains would be matched by a corresponding change in ultimate plastic shear strain. Because the reference data did not measure failure shear strain, no clear conclusion can be drawn with regard to the effect on joint strength caused by load rates, and the statement that load rate independent analysis “cannot be said to be generally conservative” is not proven. While the shear stresses and strains may change with load rate effects, there is no evidence that those changes relate to the overall *load capacity* of the joint. The conclusions in [8] that the above analytical approach is unconservative would only be true if the changes in elastic limits for shear stress and shear strain τ_p and γ_e were not associated with a concurrent change in maximum strain capacity of the adhesive.

If one were to *assume* that the maximum shear strain capacity was not changed, the effect on the joint load capacity on the basis of the data points shown in reference [8] is about 5% for the worst case.

BONDED JOINT FAILURE MECHANISMS

Bonded joints may fail by a number of mechanisms. As shown above, if the adhesive shear strain at the end of the joint exceeds the maximum shear strain capacity (as determined by a thick adherend test), the failure will occur through the adhesive layer. This type of failure is termed cohesion failure. If the joint is subjected to out-of-plane tensile stresses, the joint will fail in peel. Both of these cases can be analysed using relatively simple models, [7, 11]. If the joint surface has not been adequately prepared, or if the preparation process is susceptible to in-service interfacial hydration, then the failure will occur at the interface, which is known as adhesion failure. This failure method can not be predicted, and must be stringently avoided by use of surface preparation processes which have been correctly validated, [12,13].

DESIGNING BONDED JOINTS WITHOUT LOAD RATE EFFECTS

For thin adherends (typically less than 3.8 mm (0.15 in.) for aluminium alloys) there is a fourth failure mode which is frequently overlooked in structural design. If the material being joined is thin and the overlap length is large enough to ensure generation of the complete elastic trough, the failure may be forced to occur in the adherends, and not in the adhesive, (see Fig. 4) [14]. This approach is the basis for repair design in RAAF ENG STD C5033.

Figure 4. Potential joint strength for adhesive bonds between adherends of varying thickness (from [14]). For thin adherends, the joint strength is limited by the strength of the adherends. For these conditions, the adhesive is not the critical element, and minor variations in adhesive properties will not be relevant to the overall strength of the joint.

To achieve the required load capacity, a bonded joint must have sufficient overlap length. To guarantee that the required overlap is achieved, ENG STD C5033 calls for the plastic zone overlap length to be sufficient to carry ALL load at unnotched material ultimate strength of the parent material (see Fig. 5). The elastic zone then provides a margin of safety and also acts to minimise creep effects. A further check is made by calculation of the load capacity of the joint. If the load capacity of the adhesive is greater than the load capacity of the parent material, and the overlap length is sufficient to ensure that the elastic trough approaches zero away from the ends of the joint, then the structure will fail before the adhesive, and therefore *the adhesive will never be the critical element in the joint*. RAAF ENG STD C5033 uses a factor of 1.2 times the unnotched strength of the parent material to ensure that the adhesive is not critical. If the adhesive is never the critical element in the joint, then the minimal changes in adhesive properties due to loading rate effects are irrelevant. Similar arguments can be advanced concerning the relevance of failure theories for adhesive bonded joints.

WHERE ARE LOAD RATES IMPORTANT?

From the above discussions, it may be concluded that the strain rate effects described (in Reference [8]) are not significant in repairs and bonded joints if the adhesive is designed such that its load capacity is greater than the parent material. For typical aluminium alloys, if sufficient overlap exists, joints between adherends up to about 3.75 mm (0.15 inches) can be designed such that the adhesive is not critical. Thus, load rate effects are irrelevant to joints in most common structural bonds in aircraft. For joints where the adhesive is the critical element, load rate effects may be relevant, if testing to failure actually showed that the load capacity of the adhesive was effected.

However, there is one aspect of the work in reference [8] which is of relevance to joint analysis. The work shows that a standard loading rate may be required to minimise errors for tests to generate design data for adhesives. Once that data is generated, load rate effects may be ignored.

Figure 5. Methodology for determination of overlap length such that the adhesive is never critical under any load condition.

CONCLUSIONS

The assertion [8] that load rate independent analyses are unconservative has not been proven, because the test method used in the original work did not measure all relevant parameters required to ascertain the load capacity of the adhesive. While the elastic properties have been shown to change, without proper experimental procedure to measure the effects on plastic behaviour, no conclusion can be drawn. From the explanation of the differences between real bonded joints and the artificial conditions which exist in thick adherend specimens, together with the design methodology outlined for assuring that the adhesive is never the critical element in the joint, it may be concluded that loading rate effects have little relevance to bonded joint and repair designs. There may be a requirement to use a standard loading rate for tests to generate adhesive design data.

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